

Effectiveness of a holistic approach in leprosy control- Integration of monitoring of leprosy control activities within epidemiological reviews in Regional Directorate of Health services Colombo

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Background

- At district level, surveillance and control activities are conducted and technically mentored by multiple stakeholders at national level.
- “Epidemiological reviews” offer a platform to integrate related domains.
- Such integration helps avoid duplication and streamline field-level efforts.

Description of the initiative

Three consultative sessions held across 18 MOH areas with district, provincial, and national stakeholders input following which was integrated since 01st of January 2025.

Identified entry points for leprosy data:

- Weekly Epidemiological Review Format
- MOH office progress monitoring boards
- Weekly district review PowerPoint slides
- Monthly Heads of Institution (HoI) meetings
- Annual appraisal assessment formats of RDHS-Colombo

Supervision Format		
MOH Area.....	Date.....	Week ending notification.....
Attendees' names	Designation	Signature

Figure 01

Table 5: Tuberculosis (TB), Leprosy and Rabies surveillance

PHI area	No. of TB notified	No. of cases for which contact tracing completed	No. of Leprosy notified	No. of cases for which contact tracing completed	Dog vaccinations & sterilization activities
1					
2					

Figure 02

Methods used for the evaluation

Coverage Indicators:

- Inclusion of all 18 MOH areas with participation of diverse staff categories across institutions
- Integration of leprosy data into multiple routine platforms

Timeliness Indicators:

- Weekly updates via epidemiological reviews and district-level PowerPoint slides
- Monthly reporting through Head of Institutions meetings
- Annual appraisal formats aligned with review cycles

Qualitative Field Observations:

- Team supervisions revealed improved awareness and ownership of integrated formats
- Staff engagement strengthened through consultative and mentoring sessions
- Field-level feedback informed practical adjustments to monitoring tools

Results

- Integration approach led to improvement in contact screening
- Weekly reviews conducted across all MOH areas
- District team provides continuous feedback reports
- Supervision boards updated regularly at MOH offices

Lessons Learnt

Leprosy surveillance is embedded within broader public health indicators which provides a holistic and efficient approach to disease control.

Monitoring is linked to routine review processes which ensures continuity, accountability, and long-term sustainability.